

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN MEDICINE AND THE ISSUES OF ITS INFLUENCE ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY AND HEALTH.

Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich
(PhD), associate professor
Xoshimova Laziza Akbar qizi
Master of JDPU
lazizaxoshimova1997@gmail.com
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Abstract. In this article, the impact of music on human psyche and health, the effect of music therapy on the treatment of certain diseases or the improvement of the patient's quality of life using the Uzbek national musical heritage, and the algorithm of broadcasting the recommended works are formed.

Key words: music therapy, medicine, classics, psychology, therapy, temperament, classical music, chronic diseases.

Music therapy is a health care profession in which music therapists use music and its aspects—physical, emotional, mental, social, aesthetic, and spiritual—to help patients improve and maintain health. This is considered expressive therapy. Cognitive function, motor skills, emotional and affective development, behavioral and social skills, and patients' quality of life have been clinically proven to improve through music therapy.

The effectiveness of music therapy is evidence-based and accepted as both an art and a science. Music therapy is used in some medical hospitals, cancer centers, schools, alcohol and drug rehabilitation programs, psychiatric hospitals, and correctional facilities.

Music therapy is an adjunctive therapeutic treatment that is used as a means of interaction, expression and communication among existing traditional forms of medical psychotherapy.

According to historical sources, it is appropriate to use national music samples of each nation based on the national mentality of each nation. Consequently, the national values and traditions of each nation are embedded in the blood of the nation.

It should be said that the music played to the patients is not only in the foreign classical style, but also in the national-traditional and modern-pop performance style of the Uzbek people. Because the customs and values formed in the Uzbek nation for many centuries, the perception of the eternal "I", the Uzbek mentality and nationality, the spirit of respect for ancestors, are embedded in the heart of every soul who is a part of the nation.

Therefore, listening to the works of composers and composers, poets and singers, who have the full qualities and feelings of the Uzbek nation, which have been passed down from mouth to mouth for years in their native language, will definitely have a psychological and physical effect on the people of this nation.

The results of the study showed that when Uzbek folk music and modern Uzbek music were listened to, patients felt lighter, the disease seemed to recede a little, the feeling of fear decreased in patients with mental disorders, and the uncertainty was eliminated by reducing the feelings of anxiety in patients with chronic diseases, related to emotional experiences. It

has been proven that it reduces headaches, improves general vitality and well-being, increases physical activity, improves mood, restores lost energy, and improves blood metabolism.

During the study, patients treated in hospitals, outpatients or at home under the supervision of a medical professional at various times, including:

- during morning physical activity, around 08:00;
- around 10:00-11:00 in the afternoon;
- in the afternoon, around 16:00-17:00;
- at the end of daytime treatments;
- during procedures under the supervision of a medical officer;
- before bedtime, around 9:00 p.m

while listening to different music including:

- in the state of light physical training;
- after a walk in the nature in the fresh air;
- in the case that the patients themselves are also accompanied;
- while viewing various works of art (painting, sculpture, etc.);
- at the end of evening treatments, in stable condition

during the period of the patient's illness, including:

- period of the first onset of the disease;
- period of attack of the disease;
- period of recovery from illness;
- early rehabilitation (recovery) period after recovery from illness;
- after recovery from illness, late rehabilitation (recovery) period;
- during the period when he returned to a completely healthy life

from samples of Uzbek music and art of various genres, depending on the extent to which they affect patients:

- works of status;
- examples of Uzbek compositional creativity;
- folk songs (terma, lapar, folklore, yalla);
- academic-vocal works;
- modern-pop works were listened to.

Of course, the genre of works recommended for the treatment of patients through music was developed taking into account the age of the patient, temperament of the patient, types of diseases, the general condition of the patient, the time of listening to music, and the state of listening to music.

Algorithm for broadcasting works recommended for treating patients through music

Recommend ed work genres	Patient age	The patient temperame nt	The patient when sick situation	Music listening time	Music listening status
Status works	40-71 and from him high	Choleric , sanguine , melancholic , phlegmatic	Of the disease first start period	Evening before bedtime , around	Evening procedures in the end , stable

				9:00 p.m	condition
Folk songs (terma, lapar , folklore , yalla)	7 years old 70 years old	Melancholic , phlegmatic , sanguine , choleric	From illness after recovery , early rehabilitation period	From a dream then around 16:00- 17:00 Daytime procedure s at the end	Patients they are also good in the state of being hirgoyi
Uzbek composer creativity samples	25-40 years old range	Angvinic , melancholic	From illness recovery period	Under the supervisio n of a medical officer during treatments	Various art works (photo , sculpture etc.) in the state of watching
Academic- vocal works	18-50 years old range	X is choleric , melancholic	From illness After recovery , evening rehabilitation period	Daytime Around 10:00- 11:00	Clean in the air nature in the bosom walk from doing after
Modern - e strada works	15-55 years old range	F legmatic , sanguine	Full healthy to life returned period	In the morning physical during peak hours , around 08:00	Physical in the state of light training

First of all, the patients were advised to listen to national heritage works of Uzbek national heritage, followed by folk songs, samples of Uzbek composer's creativity, and contemporary pop works. Our national classical music, which is an integral part of the cultural heritage of our people, occupies a particularly important place in our spiritual life with its ancient history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style and rich creative traditions.

In conclusion, it can be said that it would be appropriate if Uzbek classical music was listened to according to the same approach to the owners of four types of

temperament together with the age group. Apart from that, people with a high musical taste can fully enjoy Uzbek national classics by listening to them.

In short, it is necessary to study music not only as an art form, but also as a natural factor that elevates human psychology. After all, music helps us to deal with the various tones and sounds of mother nature, to get to their essence and to ensure the balance of our inner world with relationships between people.

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